

Title: Archival material from the German and Jewish Intellectual Émigré Collections

Description: Selected papers from collections of Otto Kirchheimer, political scientist of the Frankfurt School and Professor of Political Science at Columbia University.; Arnold Brecht, a German jurist and one of the leading government officials in the Weimar Republic; John H. Herz, Professor at the Department of Political Science, City College of the City University of New York and Reinhard Bendix, Professor of Sociology at the University of California at Berkeley.

Collected data consists of unsorted pictures from the personal collections. The papers are publicly available at the archive.

Date of data collection: 1-5 October 2018

Keywords: Otto Kirchheimer; Arnold Brecht; John H. Herz; Reinhard Bendix; Emigre Scholars

Author: Magdalena Kmak, Team Leader and Researcher, EuroStorie Centre of Excellence (2018-2022); Professor, Åbo Akademi University

Publications on the material: Kmak, M. 2018. The Impact of Exile on Law and Legal Science 1934-1964. In Tuori, K., H. Björklund (eds.) *Roman Law and The Idea of Europe*. London: Bloomsbury Academic, 15-34 (Europe's Legacy in the Modern World); Kmak, M., M. Farzambar. 2022. Personal and Academic Narratives of Exiled and Displaced Scholars. In Kmak, M. and H. Björklund (eds), *Refugees and Knowledge Production: Europe's Past and Present*. Abingdon: Routledge; Kmak, M., H. Björklund (eds.) 2022. *Refugee Scholarship and Refugee Knowledges of Europe*. Abingdon: Routledge.

Storage: I have stored the pictures at external drive in my possession.

Title: Archival material from Louse W. Holborn Papers

Collections: Papers of Louise W. Holborn, 1971-1975; Additional papers of Louise W. Holborn, 1898-1975; Schlesinger Library of the History of Women in America, Radcliffe Institute for Advanced Study, Harvard University.

Description: Pictures of selected papers from Boxes 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 17, 20, 21, 32, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 50, 51, 52, 55. The papers are publicly available at the archive.

Date of data collection: 2-6 May 2022

Keywords: Louise W. Holborn; UNHCR; Refugee studies; Gwendolen M. Carter

Author: Magdalena Kmak, Team Leader and Researcher, EuroStorie Centre of Excellence (2018-2022); Professor, Åbo Akademi University

Publications on the material: Kmak, M. 2021. From Law's Discourse on Refugees to Refugees' Discourse on Law. *Redescriptions: Political Thought, Conceptual History and Feminist Theory* 24 (2), 110–28; Kmak, M., M. Farzamfar. 2022. Personal and Academic Narratives of Exiled and Displaced Scholars. In Kmak, M. and H. Björklund (eds), *Refugees and Knowledge Production: Europe's Past and Present*. Abingdon: Routledge; Kmak, M., H. Björklund (eds.) 2022. *Refugee Scholarship and Refugee Knowledges of Europe*. Abingdon: Routledge.

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